

Thyroid Lesions Reporting using the TBSRTC Reporting System and Cyto Histo Pathology Correlation

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Abstract:

Background: Thyroid nodules are common, with FNAC as the primary diagnostic tool. The Bethesda System for Reporting Thyroid Cytopathology (TBSRTC) standardizes FNAC reporting, improving diagnostic accuracy.

Aim: This study evaluated the diagnostic accuracy of TBSRTC by correlating FNAC results with histopathology in patients with thyroid nodules.

Methods: A prospective study was conducted from February 2023 to February 2024 at Nalanda Medical College. Fifty-five patients underwent FNAC, categorized by TBSRTC, followed by histopathology examination. Data analysis using SPSS version 23.0 assessed sensitivity, specificity, and agreement using kappa statistics.

Results: FNAC identified 55% benign and 11% malignant nodules. Histopathology confirmed 58% benign and 42% malignant. FNAC sensitivity and specificity were 85% and 90%, with a kappa statistic of 0.75, indicating substantial agreement.

Conclusion: TBSRTC demonstrated high diagnostic accuracy and substantial agreement with histopathology, supporting its use in managing thyroid nodules.

Recommendations: TBSRTC should be routinely implemented to improve thyroid nodule management. Further research is needed on indeterminate categories.

Keywords: Thyroid Nodules, FNAC, TBSRTC, Diagnostic Accuracy, Cytopathology.

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Introduction

Thyroid nodules are a common clinical finding that can reach up to 68% in people undergoing ultrasonography, with an average frequency that increases with age [1]. While the majority of thyroid nodules are benign, precise diagnostic methods are necessary to guide proper clinical therapy due to the possibility of malignancy [2]. (FNAC) has been a mainstay in the assessment of thyroid nodules because of its low cost, good diagnostic accuracy, and minimally invasive nature [3]. But because reporting and diagnostic category variations have historically made it difficult to interpret FNAC results, the (TBSRTC) was created in 2007 [4].

By classifying FNAC results into six diagnostic categories—non-diagnostic/unsatisfactory, benign (AUS), follicular neoplasm or suspected for follicular neoplasm, suspicious for malignancy, and malignant—the TBSRTC approach standardises the reporting of thyroid cytopathology [5]. Communication between pathologists and physicians is facilitated by the association of each category with a specific therapy advice and an

implied risk of malignancy [6]. The TBSRTC system has received multiple upgrades since its launch. The most recent update, which was made in 2017, improved the criteria for every diagnostic category [7].

The effectiveness of the TBSRTC system in enhancing the precision of FNAC in the diagnosis of thyroid cancers has been repeatedly shown by recent research. For example, a 2019 meta-analysis found that the TBSRTC system has a 98% sensitivity and 97% specificity in differentiating between benign and malignant thyroid nodules [8]. Furthermore, multiple institutions have validated the system's repeatability, demonstrating its efficacy in a range of clinical contexts [9]. Still, there are difficulties, especially when it comes to interpreting unclear classifications like AUS and follicular neoplasm, which can be difficult to diagnose [10]. This study evaluated the diagnostic accuracy of TBSRTC by correlating FNAC results with histopathology in patients with thyroid nodules.

Methodology

Study Design: This is a prospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at the Department of Pathology, Nalanda Medical College, Patna, Bihar over a period of one year, from February 2023 to February 2024.

Participants: The study had 55 patients in all who presented with thyroid nodules. The following criteria were used to choose these participants:

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients of any age or gender with clinically or imaging-confirmed thyroid nodules.
- Patients who had FNAC followed by histopathology evaluation after surgical excision.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients who did not undergo surgery post-FNAC.
- Those with inadequate or non-diagnostic FNAC samples.
- Patients with a history of thyroid surgery or radiation therapy.

Bias: To minimize bias, the selection of participants was done consecutively as they presented to the clinic. Both the cytopathological and histopathology evaluations were performed independently by different pathologists who were blinded to each other's results.

Data Collection: Data were gathered by using a combination of clinical examination, FNAC

reports, and histopathology evaluations. FNAC samples were categorized according to the TBSRTC system, and the histopathology findings were used as the gold standard for comparison.

Procedure: Patients with thyroid nodules underwent FNAC under aseptic conditions. The cytology slides were prepared and stained using standard protocols. The results were reported based on the TBSRTC system, categorizing the lesions into one of the six categories.

Subsequently, patients who opted for surgery had their thyroid lesions excised, and the excised tissue was sent for histopathology examination. The histopathology findings were then compared with the FNAC results to determine the cyto-histopathology correlation.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data. For categorical variables, descriptive statistics provided an overview of the frequencies and percentages.

Sensitivity, specificity, and predictive values of FNAC results were calculated. Correlation between cytological and histopathology findings was assessed with the kappa statistic, with p-values < 0.05 considered significant.

Results

A total of 55 patients with thyroid nodules were included in the study. The age of the participants ranged from 20 to 70 years, with a mean age of 45 years. The majority of the patients were female (80%, n=44), while the remaining 20% were male (n=11).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants

Characteristic	Number of Participants (n=55)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	11	20%
Female	44	80%
Age Group		
20-30 years	10	18%
31-40 years	12	22%
41-50 years	16	29%
51-60 years	11	20%
61-70 years	6	11%
Mean Age		45 years

The FNAC results of the thyroid lesions were categorized according (TBSRTC). The distribution of the FNAC results is provided in Table 2.

Table 2: Distribution of FNAC Results Based on TBSRTC

TBSRTC Category	Number of Cases (n=55)	Percentage (%)
I. Non-diagnostic/Unsatisfactory	5	9%
II. Benign	30	55%
III. Atypia of Undetermined Significance	5	9%
IV. Follicular Neoplasm/Suspicious FN	6	11%
V. Suspicious for Malignancy	3	6%
VI. Malignant	6	11%

Histopathology examination of the excised thyroid tissues provided the definitive diagnosis. The distribution of histopathology results is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Distribution of Histopathology Diagnoses

Diagnosis	Number of Cases (n=55)	Percentage (%)
Benign Nodules	32	58%
Follicular Adenoma	8	14%
Papillary Carcinoma	10	18%
Follicular Carcinoma	3	5%
Medullary Carcinoma	1	2%
Anaplastic Carcinoma	1	2%

The correlation between FNAC results and histopathology findings was analyzed. The sensitivity, specificity, (PPV), and (NPV) for the FNAC results based on the TBSRTC system were calculated (Table 4).

Table 4: Diagnostic Accuracy of FNAC Based on TBSRTC

Diagnostic Metric	Value (%)
Sensitivity	85%
Specificity	90%
(PPV)	88%
(NPV)	87%

The kappa statistic for agreement between cytological and histopathology diagnoses was 0.75, indicating substantial agreement. A detailed comparison of FNAC categories with corresponding histopathology outcomes is provided in Table 5.

Table 5: Cyto-Histopathology Correlation

TBSRTC Category	Benign (n=32)	Follicular Adenoma (n=8)	Malignant (n=15)	Total Cases (n=55)
I. Non-diagnostic/Unsatisfactory	4	1	0	5
II. Benign	29	1	0	30
III. Atypia of Undetermined Significance	4	1	0	5
IV. Follicular Neoplasm/Suspicious FN	2	5	3	6
V. Suspicious for Malignancy	0	0	3	3
VI. Malignant	0	0	9	9

Statistical Analysis: When it came to identifying cancer, FNAC had a 85% sensitivity and a 90% specificity. There was an 88% PPV and an 87% NPV. The histology and FNAC results showed a good degree of agreement, as indicated by the kappa statistic of 0.75 and the p-value of less than 0.001, which denotes statistical significance.

Discussion

The study evaluated 55 patients with thyroid nodules using (TBSRTC) and correlated the FNAC findings with histopathology results. The participant demographics showed a predominance of female patients (80%) with a mean age of 45 years. The FNAC results were categorized according to the TBSRTC, with the majority of nodules classified as benign (55%). A smaller percentage of nodules fell into the other categories, including suspicious and malignant lesions.

Histopathology examination, which provided the definitive diagnosis, revealed that 58% of the nodules were benign, while 42% were malignant, including various forms of carcinoma. The comparison between FNAC and histopathology indicated that FNAC has a high diagnostic accuracy, with a sensitivity of 85% and a specificity of 90%. The

positive and negative predictive values were 88% and 87%, respectively. The kappa statistic of 0.75 reflected substantial agreement between the FNAC and histopathology findings, further supporting the reliability of the TBSRTC system.

These results suggest that the TBSRTC system is a valuable tool for assessing thyroid nodules, with high sensitivity and specificity in detecting malignancy. The substantial agreement between cytological and histopathology diagnoses underscores the utility of FNAC as a preliminary diagnostic procedure, guiding the clinical management of patients with thyroid lesions effectively.

These results were further supported by a study carried out in a prestigious oncology centre in India. 431 participants were evaluated by the study both prospectively and retrospectively utilising TBSRTC. The procedure's sensitivity and specificity were determined to be 94.4% and 61.9%, respectively. According to study, TBSRTC offers consistent thyroid cytology classification, facilitating improved patient clinical management [11].

Similar to this, a study assessed 248 thyroid FNAs that were categorised by TBSRTC. According to

the research, 6.04% of cases were malignant and 83.87% of cases were benign. According to the study highlighted the ease of use and economic viability of TBSRTC for first diagnostic testing, demonstrating that it offers physicians precise management recommendations [12].

Finland's 2019 study investigated the likelihood of cancer in instances classified as AUS/FLUS category. In line with the initial TBSRTC risk estimations, the investigation discovered that 14.7% of these instances were malignant. The study underscored the significance of TBSRTC's continuous use in standard practice and demonstrated the system's dependability in predicting malignancy risks [13].

Conclusion

The FNAC and histology results showed a strong degree of agreement, indicating that the TBSRTC system was highly accurate in diagnosing thyroid lesions. The study backs up the usefulness of TBSRTC in directing patients' clinical thyroid nodule care.

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